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First records of *Forcipomyia dichromata* REMM (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) in Poland and Spain

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17310034>

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Abstract: *Forcipomyia* (subgenus *Forcipomyia*) *dichromata* REMM, in REMM & ZHOGOLEV 1968 is recorded for the first time in Poland and Spain. Earlier, this Western Palaearctic species was reported from Europe (Ukraine, France, Norway), Middle East (Israel, Turkey, Yemen), and Central Asia (Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan). The male was diagnosed and illustrated. Currently the number of biting midges (Ceratopogonidae) reported from Poland increased to 221 and from Spain to 194 species.

Key words: biting midge, Northern Poland, Sierra de Tejada, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

Biting midges (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) are small nematocerous flies which are common in all kinds of aquatic, semiaquatic and moist terrestrial habitats worldwide. Their recent world fauna is relatively well studied and comprises 6276 extant species (BORKENT & DOMINIAK 2020, BORKENT *et al.* 2022). Almost 600 valid species have been reported from Europe (SZADZIEWSKI *et al.* 2013). The last checklist of biting midges of Poland includes 220 species (SZADZIEWSKI & DOMINIAK 2016) and of Spain 193 species (DELÉCOLLE 2002). Here, the presented short note provides first records of *Forcipomyia dichromata* REMM from Poland and Spain.

MATERIAL AND SITES

NE Poland: Pomerania, Trojmiejski Landscape Park, Gdynia, Łęg nad Sweliną reserve (Fig. 1), 54°27'41"N, 18°32'07"E, UTM CF43, 10.09.2011, at light, 2 males, leg. M. Gwizdalska-Kentzer. **SW Spain:** Andalusia, Malaga province, Sierra de Tejada, village Puerta de don Manuel, 36°53'18"N, 4°08'47"W, 20.04.1984, forest, caught by hand, 1 male, leg. P. Sura. The examined specimens are mounted on slides in Canada balsam and deposited in the collection of extant invertebrates at the Department of Invertebrate Zoology and Parasitology, University of Gdańsk.

Fig. 1. Collecting site in Łęg nad Swelini reserve, N Poland (April 2025).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Forcipomyia (Forcipomyia) dichromata REMM, 1968

Forcipomyia (subg. *Forcipomyia* MEIGEN) *dichromata* REMM, in REMM & ZHOGOLEV 1968: 826 (male, female, Crimea in Ukraine). ALWIN *et al.* 2016: 363 (records from Israel, Yemen, Turkey); BORKENT & DOMINIAK 2020: 76 (in catalogue); THUNES *et al.* 2021: 19 (record from Norway); NAVAÏ 2021: 238 (female, diagnosis, record from Afghanistan).

Forcipomyia (subg. *Microhelea* KIEFFER) *dichromata* REMM. REMM 1988: 101 (subgeneric placement, records from Ukraine, France, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan). Unfortunately, country records from Tajikistan and Uzbekistan are “empty records” because they have no detailed localities.

This moderately small species is a typical member of the subgenus *Forcipomyia* s. str.: wing length of male 1.6-1.7 mm, CR 0.4-0.5; wing membrane covered with slender scale-like macrotrichia; body brown, humeri yellowish, legs pale brownish, genitalia dark brown; tarsal ratio (TR) similar on all legs: TR(1) 0.7, TR(2) 0.6, TR(3) 0.6-0.7; male genitalia typical of the subgenus (Fig. 2C), aedeagus triangular (Fig. 2D).

Males of the species are distinct in having broadly fused parameres, apices of parameres pointed, stout (Fig. 2E); third palpal segment with small sensory pit located on swollen base of the segment (Fig. 2A, B). The species is close to *F. fuliginosa* (MEIGEN) in having similar male genitalia and low tarsal ratios. They differ mostly in the shape of third palpal segment. In *F. fuliginosa* sensory pit is located on distal half of third palpal segment while in *F. dichromata* it is located on proximal half. Moreover, the base of fused parameres in *F. dichromata* is almost W-shaped while in *F. fuliginosa* U-shaped.

Fig. 2. Male of *Forcipomyia dichromata* REMM. A, B – third palpal segment, C – ventral aspect of genitalia, D – aedeagus, E – parameres.

Biting midges of the subgenus *Forcipomyia* s. str. have terrestrial larvae feeding on fungi growing on rotting debris of plant origin, for example inside of stems or roots, in ant nests, in cow or horse dung, under rotting bark of trees (SZADZIEWSKI *et al.* 1997). Immature stages of *Forcipomyia dichromata* have not been reported and as a result their breeding habitat is unknown. The species has broad distribution in Western Palaearctic, however it is rarely reported. It was reported from Europe (Ukraine, France, Norway), Middle East (Israel, Turkey, Yemen), and Central Asia (Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan). From Poland and Spain it is recorded for the first time. Currently the number of biting midges reported from Poland (SZADZIEWSKI & DOMINIAK 2016) increased to 221 and from Spain (DELÉCOLLE 2002) to 194 species. In addition, the number of Ceratopogonidae recorded from the Łęg nad Sweliną reserve in N Poland (GWIZDALSKA-KENTZER 2011) increased to 50 species.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are grateful to professor Piotr Sura from Kraków for collecting in Spain in 1984 a male of *Forcipomyia dichromata*.

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Accepted: 27 July 2025; published: 10 October 2025

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